

Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China

also known as “Longmen Shiku 龙门石窟”

By Dong Wang, Shanghai University; Fairbank Center at Harvard University (since 2002)

Entry tags: Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Forum, Tomb, City, Monastery, Shrines, Open-Air Sanctuary, Chinese Religion, Chinese State Religion, Chinese Folk Religions, Daoist Traditions, Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Chinese Christian Traditions, Chinese Nestorian Traditions, Monument, Temple, Altar, Religious Place, Religious Group

This entry seeks to provide notes, text and image archives, discuss scholarly debates, and link relevant resources surrounding the Longmen Grottoes, a major Chinese Buddhist historical and UNESCO World Heritage site in Luoyang, Henan Province, from antiquity to the present. Meaning “dragon gate,” the name Longmen refers to the scenic mountain ravine between the East (303.5 meters altitude) and West Hills (Longmenshan, 263.9 meters altitude) through which the Yi River flows, a place also known as Yique, about thirteen kilometers (around 8 miles, or 25 li) south of Luoyang in Henan Province, the central province of the North China Plain, the heartland and imperial capital of thirteen Chinese dynasties, mostly south of the Yellow River. Approximately and arguably dating from 493 CE during the Northern Wei Dynasty (386–534) as a Buddhist votive site, the Longmen Grottoes as we see today comprise an assemblage of more than 2,000 stone niches and caves, over 100,000 fine-grained limestone sculptures and reliefs, and around 2,800 memorial steles (stone tablets) containing more than 300,000 words of inscribed text. The caves are carved into a 1-kilometer stretch of limestone cliffs on either side of the Yi River. While many of Longmen’s sculptures are low relief carvings on the walls and ceilings of the caves, some are spectacularly hewn out of the limestone in situ. The inscriptions are also mostly chiseled into walls and ceilings, alongside the images to which they refer. The production of stone images at Longmen continued in the Eastern Wei (534–550), Western Wei (535–556), Northern Qi (550–577), Northern Zhou (557–581), and Sui (581–618) dynasties, tailing off after the Tang dynasty (618–907) as Luoyang was repeatedly subject to war and communal violence and gradually waned in status, although new carving projects were likely undertaken until the early seventeenth century during the Ming dynasty (1368–1644). Slighted and denounced as a squandering of resources on gaudy frippery for centuries by many Chinese elites in history, the large group of stone icons, decorated cave chapels, votive niches, walls, ceilings, inscribed steles, pillars, and floors at Longmen received irregular maintenance and repair, probably the most significant due to the Qianlong emperor’s visit in 1750. Rediscovered by American, British, Chinese, French, German, Japanese, and Swedish scholars, collectors and connoisseurs around the turn of the twentieth century, Longmen in modern times came to embody the values of universalism, modernity, and the modern impulse for both China and the world. The treasures at Longmen—preeminently stone sculptures dating from the fifth to the tenth centuries CE—were the object of a global quest that can be compared with the exploits of Indiana Jones. In 2001, UNESCO decided to add the Longmen Grottoes to the World Heritage List of properties deemed to have outstanding universal value.

Date Range: 1 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province, PRC

Region tags: China, East Asia, Luoyang, Henan Province, Longmen Grottoes

Located on the Central Plain (Zhongyuan 中原) in

interior North China, Luoyang in Henan Province, the host city of the Longmen Grottoes, was a key geopolitical, administrative, and cultural center throughout the first millennium BCE and CE. It, by the first half of the twentieth century, deteriorated into what was called a "Chinese Babylon." The founding of the People's Republic of China, however, added new strategic, economic, and cultural importance to Luoyang. As of 2016, Luoyang grew to cover 800 square kilometers with a population of over 6.5 million, of whom 2 million lived in its urban centers.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source
- Body of water (as distinct from source)
- Marsh or bog
- Cave
- Other [specify]: grass, plants, flowers

Reference: Wang, Dong. Longmen's Stone Buddhas and Cultural Heritage. Rowman & Littlefield, 2020. https://books.google.com/books/about/Longmen_s_Stone_Buddhas_and_Cultural_Her.html?hl=&id=s5XnDwAAQBAJ. fig.0.1

Reference: Hughes, April D.. Worldly Saviors and Imperial Authority in Medieval Chinese Buddhism. University of Hawaii Press, 2021. https://books.google.com/books/about/Worldly_Saviors_and_Imperial_Authority_i.html?hl=&id=LDcWEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Rothschild, N. Harry. Emperor Wu Zhao and Her Pantheon of Devis, Divinities, and Dynastic Mothers. Columbia University Press, 2015. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=mHmpBgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: McNair, Amy. Donors of Longmen. University of Hawaii Press, 2007. https://books.google.com/books/about/Donors_of_Longmen.html?hl=&id=qsEGldhcgMoC.

Type of elevation

- Hill
- Mountain
- Gorge

- Rock face
- Other [specify]: Ravine

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Among the Tang caves at Longmen, the Fengxian Temple, also known as Jiujianfang, housing the 17.14-meter-high statue of the Huayan (Avataṃsaka) and esoteric Buddha Vairocana, is the most photographed, iconic monument of Longmen. Completed in 675/676 (and most probably started in 666), the Fengxian Temple was constructed by a team of workmen including Li Junzan, Cheng Renwei, and Yao Shiji, led by Wei Ji, Fan Xuanze, and two prominent master monks under the auspices of the Tang emperor Gaozong (r. 650–680).

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: roofs, covers, gutters, and a drainage system

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: The beginnings of the large group of Longmen's caves and icons are attributed to the Tuoba clan of the Tabgach (Tabgach, Xianbei) tribe from southern Manchuria, who established the Northern Wei dynasty in 386 CE, with its capital in Shengle (near Hohhot, Inner Mongolia); the capital was moved to Pingcheng (Datong, north Shanxi Province) in 398. Led by the Xiaowen emperor (r. 471–499), some of the Tuoba leaders sought to consolidate their dominance in North China by moving the capital from Pingcheng to Luoyang on the Yellow River in 493—home to the first Buddhist temple in China, the Temple of the White Horse (Baima Si), built in 68 AD during the Eastern Han. Despite the fluctuating patronage of Buddhism by various emperors, the Northern Wei's Tuoba ancestors had practiced a half century or more of devotion to Buddhism, which was transmitted to China via Central and West Asia from India.

– Memorial

Notes: The Tuoba people had also mastered the art of casting statues and carving rocks into memorial images in honor of revered parents, relatives, and significant clan figures.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: A large number of structures and carvings at Longmen were destroyed caused by natural and man-made damage.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For economic reasons

– As the result of pillage

- ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Human-caused accident
 - Natural phenomena

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
 - Periodically

- ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Buddha

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Buddha, Bodhisattvas, Ānanda, Arhat, and other Buddhist, Daoist, Christian, and other figures.

Notes: The grand entrance arch of the Huoshao Cave from the Northern Wei contains a relief of the Daoist immortals, the Queen Mother of the West and the King Father of the East, riding on dragons amid auspicious clouds.

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: McNair, Amy. *Donors of Longmen: Faith, Politics, and Patronage in Medieval Chinese Buddhist Sculpture*. Honolulu, Hawaii: University of Hawaii, 2007.
- Source 2: Longmen shiku yanjiusuo (龙门石窟研究所), Liu Jinglong (刘景龙), and Li Yukun (李玉昆), comp. *Longmen Shiku beike tiji huilu [龙门石窟碑刻题记汇录 A collection of epigraphic inscriptions at the Longmen Grottos]*. Beijing: Zhongguo dabaike quanshu chubanshe, 1998, 2 vols.
- Source 3: Longmen shiku yanjiusuo, ed. *Longmen liusan diaoxiang ji [龙门流散雕像集 An account of the lost statues of the Longmen Grottoes]*. Shanghai: Shanghai renmin meishu shubanshe, 1993.
- Source 1: Wang, Dong. *Longmen's Stone Buddhas and Cultural Heritage: When Antiquity Met Modernity in China*. Lanham, Md.: Rowman & Littlefield, 2020.
- Source 2: Abe, Stanley K. *Ordinary Images*. Chicago, Ill.: University of Chicago Press, 2002.

- Source 3: Wong, Dorothy C. *Chinese Steles: Pre-Buddhist and Buddhist Use of a Symbolic Form*. Honolulu, Hawaii: University of Hawaii Press, 2004.
- Source 1: Wei, Shou (505--572, 魏收). *Weishu* [魏书 The history of the Wei]. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1999.
- Source 2: Lu, Chaolin (路朝霖). *Luoyang Longmen zhi* [洛阳龙门志 Records on Luoyang's Longmen]. Private ed., 1870/1877, 2 vols. Reprinted in *Zhongguo fosi congshu* [中国佛寺丛书], vol. 8. Yangzhou: Guangling shushe, 1996.
- Source 3: Lu, Chaolin. comp. and ed. *Luoyang Longmen zhi xuzuan*. [洛阳龙门志续纂 A sequel to Longmen's Longmen]. Kaifeng, 1898. Reprinted in *Zhongguo fosi congshu*, vol. 8, 1996.
- Source 1: Yang, Xuanzhi (?-? 杨衒之), annotated and trans. Xiang Rong (向荣). *Luoyang qielan ji*. [洛阳伽蓝记 The Buddhist monasteries of Luoyang]. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2012.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

- Mound
- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/uploads/nominations/1003.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Longmen's location in the city of Luoyang in 2000. The UNESCO Archives and the World Heritage Centre. WHC Nomination Documentation, file no. 1003, December 2, 2000, Longmen

Grottoes (34°28'N, 112°28' E), p. 107, accessed on January 11, 2020.

– Source 2 URL: http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=13637&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html

– Source 2 Description: Hague Convention. May 14, 1954, accessed on February 13, 2019.

– Source 3 URL: <http://whc.unesco.org/en/conventiontext/>

– Source 3 Description: UNESCO. "Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, 1972," accessed November 24, 2019.

– Source 1 URL: <http://whc.unesco.org/archive/repcom00.htm>

– Source 1 Description: UNESCO Archives. "Report of the 24th Session," WHC-2000/CONF.204/21, accessed on August 11, 2007.

– Source 2 URL: <http://whc.unesco.org/archive/opguide99.pdf>

– Source 2 Description: UNESCO Intergovernmental Committee for the Protection of World Cultural and Natural Heritage Sites. "Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention," WHC-99/2, March 1999, accessed on January 1, 2009.

– Source 3 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/stat#s2>

– Source 3 Description: UNESCO World Heritage Convention. "World Heritage List Statistics," accessed on August 13, 2019.

– Source 1 URL: http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=13039&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html

– Source 1 Description: The UNESCO 1970 Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property, accessed on August 19, 2021

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.unidroit.org/english/conventions/1995culturalproperty/1995culturalproperty-e.pdf>

– Source 2 Description: UNESCO 1995 Convention on Stolen or Illegally Exported Cultural Object of the International Institute for the Unification of Private Law (UNIDROIT).

– Source 3 URL: <https://ctext.org/wikipedia/?if=gb&res=122627&re map=gb>

– Source 3 Description: Shi, Cheng (施诚), comp. Henan fuzhi [河南府志, Gazetteer of Henanfu], 24 vols., u.p.: 1867, accessed on March 6, 2020.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– Yes

Notes: Besides the temple caves, Longmen also has burial caves for high-ranking monks.

↳ Part of body present:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, the Tuoba clan.

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– Yes

↳ Part of body present:

– I don't know

Notes: The tomb of Bai Juyi (772–846), a most famous Tang poet, is at Longmen, and allegedly he was buried there. Scholarly representations of Longmen underwent three major changes during the Song–Yuan dynastic transition, while still acknowledging the heritage of the past. One was the reinvention of Bai Juyi as a “cultural ancestor” of Longmen and a role model for those seeking independence and detachment from officialdom.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– No

Notes: Emperors such as Xiaowen were equated with the incarnation of the Tathāgata Buddha who represented the eternal essence of being, beyond all coming and going.

↳ Part of body present:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Examples can be found in Wen, Yucheng (温玉成). “Luoyang Longmen Xiangshan Si yizhi diaochao shijue” [洛阳龙门香山寺遗址调查试掘 The preliminary findings from the excavation of Luoyang Longmen’s Xiangshan Monastery]. *Kaogu*, no. 1 (1986): 40–43.

– Scientific

Notes: Examples of excavations in Longmen and Luoyang can be found in: Yang, Zuolong (杨作龙), Zhao Shuisen (赵水森), et al., comp., *Luoyang xin chutu muzhi shilu* [洛阳新出土墓志释录 Notes on the newly excavated tomb steles]. Beijing: Beijing tushuguan chubanshe, 2004; Yang, Zuolong (杨作龙), and Mao Yangguang (毛阳光), eds. *Luoyang kaogu jicheng: Qinhan Weijin Nanbeichao juan*. [洛阳考古集成:秦汉魏晋南北朝卷 Archeological findings in Luoyang: Qinhan Weijin and Northern and Southern Dynasties]. Beijing: Beijing Tushuguan chubanshe, 2007, 2 vols.; Longmen Shiku Yanjiuyuan, Beijing Daxue Kaogu Wenbo Yuan and Zhongguo shehui kexueyuan shijie zongjiao yanjiusuo, *Longmen Shiku kaogu baogao: Dongshan Leigutai qu* [龙门石窟考古: 东山擂鼓区]. Beijing: Kexue chubanshe, 2018), 6 vols.

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1980s--2010s

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavations at the Longmen Grottos, Longmen Shiku kaogu fajue 龙门石窟考古发掘

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Up till the 2010s, Longmen, about 13 kilometers (around 8 miles, or 25 li) south of the old Luoyang city, was considered rural, suburban and peri-urban, rather than urban. For example, Bai Juyi (772–846), a most prominent Tang poet was clearly aware of Longmen as being outside the city walls: “I went out of the capital’s [Luoyang] city gates and gazed nearby and far into the

distance, seeing only water and mountains. Green vegetation covers the grand Yique Pass [Longmen]. Slowly flows the clear Yi River." Since the 1980s, urbanization has been the major driver of PR. China's unceasing push for modernization and national rejuvenation, although an official urbanization policy was not announced until 2014. Longmen became a UNESCO World Heritage site in 2001 in the newly created Luolong district of the city of Luoyang. Its elevation to the WHL has involved the rehousing of over 700 households near their former homes in 8 peri-urban villages clustered around Longmen's northern entrance. The residents of these villages have experienced in situ urbanization in two major waves—in 1999–2000 and again from 2012, primarily driven by the changed status of the Longmen Grottoes, in concert with China's ongoing urban spread and the New Style Urbanization Plan.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

— No

Notes: Longmen is located about 13 kilometers (9 miles) away from the old urban fabric. During the Han and Wei, the walled city of inner Luoyang, a rectangle with a 14-kilometer perimeter and encompassing an area of 6 × 9 li (about 15 square kilometers), was home to over 109,000 households. For urbanites living in downtown Luoyang to go to Longmen throughout history, they would have to cross the Luo River. For example, Charles Lang Freer in late October and early November 1910 wrote about his travel to Longmen from the city of Luoyang: "The ponies and mules turned out better than they looked, for they dragged their heavy loads through miles of mud, over rocks and boulders, through hundreds of ruts and through the wide Lo Ho (Luo) River at the crossing place, with a patience and determination befitting their veteran years." Charles Lang Freer's travel journal, October 29, 1910, Charles Lang Freer Papers, Freer and Sackler Gallery of Art Archive, Smithsonian Institution in Washington, DC.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

— Yes

Notes: Administrative boundaries have been changing and adjusting to this day. For a long time, Longmen, the place, was in the rural area of greater Luoyang, then became peri-urban during the P.R. China era, and is poised to become completely urban thanks to the ongoing urbanization process in PRC.

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

— Yes

Notes: In the first half of the twentieth century, we know that banditry plagued the Longmen site and the large area between Longmen and the city center of Luoyang.

— Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

— Yes

Notes: In contemporary times, major wide roads and bus and subway routes were established leading to Longmen. However, in the early twentieth century, traveling to Longmen, even from the center of the city of Luoyang (then Honanfu, today the Old City District of Luoyang), was no easy task. Robberies and murders committed by bands of brigands with headquarters near Longmen were only part of the trouble to deal with during a day trip or a stay at Longmen. The

presence of half a dozen armed guards with rifles was nothing unusual for visitors to Longmen. Further, the road conditions were poor and the means of transportation challenging—a cart with two-mule tandem and sometimes sedan chairs were a luxury for the privileged few. Travelers would have to cross the River Luo southward on a scow before an around 10-kilometer bumpy journey to Longmen. Luo Zhenyu (1866-1940) wrote about his travel in 1915 to Longmen: “All visitors to Longmen went there by sedan chair; I did not know about this in the beginning, so I went there by carriage. It was very bumpy all the way along, like a boat riding on wild waves.” Luo, Zhenyu. “Wushiri menghen lu” [五十日梦痕录 A tearful record on the fifty-day trip]. In Luo Zhenyu xueshu lunwenji, vol. 11, ed. by Luo Zhenyu. Shanghai: Shanghai guji chubanshe.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

- King or emperor
- Religious specialists affiliated with political entity
- Private individual

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The corridor linking the Guanzhong Wei River valley to west Luoyang and the Yi-Luo River valley, where Luoyang was set, holds the key to understanding the emergence of historical China, its politics, society, culture, and religion. By the early sixth century, historical sources show that Luoyang and its vicinity was once filled with over one thousand Buddhist temples, in coexistence with non-religious places of habitation. Despite some distance away from the urban center, the Longmen caves were the manifestation of the spread of Buddhism in the cradle of early and medieval China, but over time the place, Longmen, as the hosting site of votive sculptures and other religious artifacts ceased to carry strong religious meanings to contemporary tourists.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

- Priests
- Slaves
- Corvee labourers
- Indentured servants
- Captured enemies
- Men
- Women

- Specialized labourers/craftspeople
- Other [specify]: official and private donors

Notes: Most images at Longmen came with inscribed epigraphs, an enormous number of donor inscriptions in stone, and other texts inscribed on the same stone side by side with the hewn rock images to which they refer. This level of epigraphic activity is largely absent at Yungang in Datong, Shanxi Province due to the culture and coarse-grained granite in the latter.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

- Yes

↳ Specify

- Revealed by semi-divine human(s)

Notes: The sage, king and sovereign, the legendary emperor, Yu the Great was closely associated with Luoyang's Longmen. To control flooding, Yu the Great is said to have organized large groups of laborers to dredge the riverbeds and open up the drainage channel that ran down the Longmen Hill. For over a millennium, the Longmen site was chiefly appreciated for its scenery, political and cultural heroes such as Yu the Great and Bai Juyi, and epigraphic inscriptions. Longmen's striking natural landscape (shanshui), rather than its stone niches and statues, was most often the center of attention. The turn of the twentieth century marked a watershed, when international studies of Longmen's caves and iconography began to appear in the fields of archaeology, sinology, religion, art, and East Asian studies.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

- No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

- Yes

↳ Specify

- Other [specify]: The founding of the Western Zhou dynasty (1046 BCE-771 BCE)

Notes: Prominently featured in Chinese mythology and early records, Luoyang and Longmen were both sacred and imperial centers, in striking contrast to their post-thirteenth century decline. Located in a narrow, mountain-rimmed basin formed by the Rivers Yi and Luo, Luoyang was the capital of thirteen dynasties, the first of which was founded over 1,500 years before the Common Era. During the seventh century, Luoyang's status reached its zenith as a shendu (divine capital). According to historical data, the construction of Luoyi (Luoyang) began in the fifth year of the Duke of Zhou's regency when King Cheng of the Zhou was a boy.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

- Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: Luoyang's Longmen as a place has been used by both believers and nonbelievers for thousands of years.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: The Longmen Grottoes started its life initially as an expression of the royal, imperial, and ordinary people's devotion mainly to Buddhism.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Buddhist scriptures [Huayan, Chan, the Pure Land, Esotericism, the Dharmalakṣaṇa school (Yogācāra), etc.] at historical Longmen.

Notes: In 840, Bai sponsored the construction of the scripture hall at the Xiangshan Monastery; he is said to have donated 5,000 copies of the Buddhist scriptures and over 800 of his own poems, composed in Luoyang, to be kept there. During the Tang dynasty the Xiangshan Monastery was located at the south end of the East Hill and the southeast end of the nine Leigutai caves. The Xiangshan Monastery that exists and is in use today at Longmen was built in 1707 on the foundations of the Qianyuan Monastery, which dated from the Tang. See Wen Yucheng, "Luoyang Longmen Xiangshan Si yizhi diaochao shijue," *Kaogu*, no. 1 (1986): 40-3.

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Yes

↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

– Yes

↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:

This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

– Yes

↳ Space underneath the structure

– Yes

↳ Other:
–Other [specify]: It varies throughout history.

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:
– Yes

↳ Built specifically for the purpose:
– Yes

↳ Repurposed:
– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:
– Yes

↳ Are they read aloud:
– Yes

↳ To a human audience
– Yes

↳ Are they studied:
– Yes

↳ Are they recopied:
– Yes

↳ Used for divination:
– Yes

↳ Other:
–Other [specify]: It depends on the specific periods of history.

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: McNair, Amy. *Donors of Longmen: Faith, Politics, and Patronage in Medieval Chinese Buddhist Sculpture*. Honolulu, Hawaii: University of Hawaii, 2007.
- Source 2: Longmen shiku yanjiusuo (龙门石窟研究所), Liu Jinglong (刘景龙), and Li Yukun (李玉昆), comp. *Longmen Shiku beike tiji huilu* [龙门石窟碑刻题记汇录 A collection of epigraphic inscriptions at the Longmen Grottos]. Beijing: Zhongguo dabaike quanshu chubanshe, 1998, 2 vols.
- Source 3: Longmen shiku yanjiusuo, ed. *Longmen liusan diaoxiang ji* [龙门流散雕像集 An account of the lost statues of the Longmen Grottoes]. Shanghai: Shanghai renmin meishu shubanshe, 1993.
- Source 1: Wang, Dong. *Longmen's Stone Buddhas and Cultural Heritage: When Antiquity Met Modernity in China*. Lanham, Md.: Rowman & Littlefield, 2020.
- Source 2: Abe, Stanley K. *Ordinary Images*. Chicago, Ill.: University of Chicago Press, 2002.
- Source 3: Wong, Dorothy C. *Chinese Steles: Pre-Buddhist and Buddhist Use of a Symbolic Form*. Honolulu, Hawaii: University of Hawaii Press, 2004.
- Source 1: Wei, Shou (505--572, 魏收). *Weishu* [魏书 The history of the Wei]. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1999.
- Source 2: Lu, Chaolin (路朝霖). *Luoyang Longmen zhi* [洛阳龙门志 Records on Luoyang's Longmen]. Private ed., 1870/1877, 2 vols. Reprinted in *Zhongguo fosi congshu* [中国佛寺丛书], vol. 8. Yangzhou: Guangling shushe, 1996.
- Source 3: Lu, Chaolin. comp. and ed. *Luoyang Longmen zhi xuzuan*. [洛阳龙门志续纂 A sequel to Longmen's Longmen]. Kaifeng, 1898. Reprinted in *Zhongguo fosi congshu*, vol. 8, 1996.
- Source 1: Yang, Xuanzhi (?-? 杨衒之), annotated and trans. Xiang Rong (向荣). *Luoyang qielan ji*. [洛阳伽蓝记 The Buddhist monasteries of Luoyang]. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2012.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/uploads/nominations/1003.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Longmen's location in the city of Luoyang in 2000. The UNESCO Archives and the World Heritage Centre. WHC Nomination Documentation, file no. 1003, December 2, 2000, Longmen Grottoes (34°28'N, 112°28' E), p. 107, accessed on January 11, 2020.
- Source 2 URL: http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=13637&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- Source 2 Description: Hague Convention. May 14, 1954, accessed on February 13, 2019.
- Source 3 URL: <http://whc.unesco.org/en/conventiontext/>
- Source 3 Description: UNESCO. "Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, 1972," accessed November 24, 2019.
- Source 1 URL: <http://whc.unesco.org/archive/repcom00.htm>
- Source 1 Description: UNESCO Archives. "Report of the 24th Session," WHC-2000/CONF.204/21, accessed on August 11, 2007.
- Source 2 URL: <http://whc.unesco.org/archive/opguide99.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: UNESCO Intergovernmental Committee for the Protection of World Cultural and Natural Heritage Sites. "Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention," WHC-99/2, March 1999, accessed on January 1, 2009.

- Source 3 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/stat#s2>
- Source 3 Description: UNESCO World Heritage Convention. “World Heritage List Statistics,” accessed on August 13, 2019.
- Source 1 URL: http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=13039&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- Source 1 Description: The UNESCO 1970 Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property, accessed on August 19, 2021
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.unidroit.org/english/conventions/1995culturalproperty/1995culturalproperty-e.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: UNESCO 1995 Convention on Stolen or Illegally Exported Cultural Object of the International Institute for the Unification of Private Law (UNIDROIT).
- Source 3 URL: <https://ctext.org/wikipedia/?if=gb&res=122627&remap=gb>
- Source 3 Description: Shi, Cheng (施诚), comp. Henan fuzhi [河南府志 Gazetteer of Henanfu], 24 vols., u.p.: 1867, accessed on March 6, 2020.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Examples can be found in Wen, Yucheng (温玉成). “Luoyang Longmen Xiangshan Si yizhi diaochao shijue” [洛阳龙门香山寺遗址调查试掘 The preliminary findings from the excavation of Luoyang Longmen’s Xiangshan Monastery]. *Kaogu*, no. 1 (1986): 40-43.

– Scientific

Notes: Examples of excavations in Longmen and Luoyang can be found in: Yang, Zuolong (杨作龙), Zhao Shuisen (赵水森), et al., comp., *Luoyang xin chutu muzhi shilu* [洛阳新出土墓志释录 Notes on the newly excavated tomb steles]. Beijing: Beijing tushuguan chubanshe, 2004; Yang, Zuolong (杨作龙), and Mao Yangguang (毛阳光), eds. *Luoyang kaogu jicheng: Qinhan Weijin Nanbeichao juan*. [洛阳考古集成:秦汉魏晋南北朝卷 Archeological findings in Luoyang: Qinhan Weijin and Northern and Southern Dynasties]. Beijing: Beijing Tushuguan chubanshe, 2007, 2 vols.; *Longmen Shiku Yanjiuyuan*, Beijing Daxue Kaogu Wenbo Yuan and Zhongguo shehui kexueyuan shijie zongjiao yanjiusuo, *Longmen Shiku kaogu baogao: Dongshan Leigutai qu* [龙门石窟考古: 东山擂鼓区]. Beijing: Kexue chubanshe, 2018), 6 vols.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1980s--2010s

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavations at the Longmen Grottos, Longmen Shiku kaogu fajue 龙门石窟考古发掘

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source
- Body of water (as distinct from source)
- Marsh or bog
- Cave
- Other [specify]: grass, plants, flowers

Reference: Wang, Dong. Longmen's Stone Buddhas and Cultural Heritage. Rowman & Littlefield, 2020. https://books.google.com/books/about/Longmen_s_Stone_Buddhas_and_Cultural_Her.html?hl=&id=s5XnDwAAQBAJ. fig.0.1

Reference: Hughes, April D.. Worldly Saviors and Imperial Authority in Medieval Chinese Buddhism. University of Hawaii Press, 2021. https://books.google.com/books/about/Worldly_Saviors_and_Imperial_Authority_i.html?hl=&id=LDcWEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Rothschild, N. Harry. Emperor Wu Zhao and Her Pantheon of Devis, Divinities, and Dynastic Mothers. Columbia University Press, 2015. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=mHmpBgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: McNair, Amy. Donors of Longmen. University of Hawaii Press, 2007. https://books.google.com/books/about/Donors_of_Longmen.html?hl=&id=qsEGldhcgMoC.

Type of elevation

- Hill
- Mountain
- Gorge
- Rock face
- Other [specify]: Ravine

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Mound
- Leveling of ground
- Terracing

- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Up till the 2010s, Longmen, about 13 kilometers (around 8 miles, or 25 li) south of the old Luoyang city, was considered rural, suburban and peri-urban, rather than urban. For example, Bai Juyi (772–846), a most prominent Tang poet was clearly aware of Longmen as being outside the city walls: “I went out of the capital’s [Luoyang] city gates and gazed nearby and far into the distance, seeing only water and mountains. Green vegetation covers the grand Yique Pass [Longmen]. Slowly flows the clear Yi River.” Since the 1980s, urbanization has been the major driver of P.R. China’s unceasing push for modernization and national rejuvenation, although an official urbanization policy was not announced until 2014. Longmen became a UNESCO World Heritage site in 2001 in the newly created Luolong district of the city of Luoyang. Its elevation to the WHL has involved the rehousing of over 700 households near their former homes in 8 peri-urban villages clustered around Longmen’s northern entrance. The residents of these villages have experienced in situ urbanization in two major waves—in 1999–2000 and again from 2012, primarily driven by the changed status of the Longmen Grottoes, in concert with China’s ongoing urban spread and the New Style Urbanization Plan.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Notes: Longmen is located about 13 kilometers (9 miles) away from the old urban fabric. During the Han and Wei, the walled city of inner Luoyang, a rectangle with a 14-kilometer perimeter and encompassing an area of 6 ×9 li (about 15 square kilometers), was home to over 109,000 households. For urbanites living in downtown Luoyang to go to Longmen throughout history, they would have to cross the Luo River. For example, Charles Lang Freer in late October and early November 1910 wrote about his travel to Longmen from the city of Luoyang: “The ponies and mules turned out better than they looked, for they dragged their heavy loads through miles of mud, over rocks and boulders, through hundreds of ruts and through the wide Lo Ho (Luo) River at the crossing place, with a patience and determination befitting their veteran years.” Charles Lang Freer’s travel journal, October 29, 1910, Charles Lang Freer Papers, Freer and Sackler Gallery of Art Archive, Smithsonian Institution in Washington, DC.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: Administrative boundaries have been changing and adjusting to this day. For a long time, Longmen, the place, was in the rural area of greater Luoyang, then became peri-urban during the P.R.

China era, and is poised to become completely urban thanks to the ongoing urbanization process in PRC.

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: In the first half of the twentieth century, we know that banditry plagued the Longmen site and the large area between Longmen and the city center of Luoyang.

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: In contemporary times, major wide roads and bus and subway routes were established leading to Longmen. However, in the early twentieth century, traveling to Longmen, even from the center of the city of Luoyang (then Honanfu, today the Old City District of Luoyang), was no easy task. Robberies and murders committed by bands of brigands with headquarters near Longmen were only part of the trouble to deal with during a day trip or a stay at Longmen. The presence of half a dozen armed guards with rifles was nothing unusual for visitors to Longmen. Further, the road conditions were poor and the means of transportation challenging—a cart with two-mule tandem and sometimes sedan chairs were a luxury for the privileged few. Travelers would have to cross the River Luo southward on a scow before an around 10-kilometer bumpy journey to Longmen. Luo Zhenyu (1866-1940) wrote about his travel in 1915 to Longmen: “All visitors to Longmen went there by sedan chair; I did not know about this in the beginning, so I went there by carriage. It was very bumpy all the way along, like a boat riding on wild waves.” Luo, Zhenyu. “Wushiri menghen lu” [五十日梦痕录 A tearful record on the fifty-day trip]. In Luo Zhenyu xueshu lunwenji, vol. 11, ed. by Luo Zhenyu. Shanghai: Shanghai guji chubanshe.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The corridor linking the Guanzhong Wei River valley to west Luoyang and the Yi-Luo River valley, where Luoyang was set, holds the key to understanding the emergence of historical China, its politics, society, culture, and religion. By the early sixth century, historical sources show that Luoyang and its vicinity was once filled with over one thousand Buddhist temples, in coexistence with non-religious places of habitation. Despite some distance away from the urban center, the Longmen caves were the manifestation of the spread of Buddhism in the cradle of early and medieval China, but over time the place, Longmen, as the hosting site of votive sculptures and other religious artifacts ceased to carry strong religious meanings to contemporary tourists.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: Among the Tang caves at Longmen, the Fengxian Temple, also known as Jiujianfang, housing the 17.14-meter-high statue of the Huayan (Avatamsaka) and esoteric Buddha Vairocana, is the most photographed, iconic monument of Longmen. Completed in 675/676 (and most probably started in 666), the Fengxian Temple was constructed by a team of workmen including Li Junzan, Cheng Renwei, and Yao Shiji, led by Wei Ji, Fan Xuanze, and two prominent master monks under the auspices of the Tang emperor Gaozong (r. 650–680).

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: roofs, covers, gutters, and a drainage system

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: The beginnings of the large group of Longmen's caves and icons are attributed to the Tuoba clan of the Tabgach (Tabgach, Xianbei) tribe from southern Manchuria, who established the Northern Wei dynasty in 386 CE, with its capital in Shengle (near

Hohhot, Inner Mongolia); the capital was moved to Pingcheng (Datong, north Shanxi Province) in 398. Led by the Xiaowen emperor (r. 471–499), some of the Tuoba leaders sought to consolidate their dominance in North China by moving the capital from Pingcheng to Luoyang on the Yellow River in 493—home to the first Buddhist temple in China, the Temple of the White Horse (Baima Si), built in 68 AD during the Eastern Han. Despite the fluctuating patronage of Buddhism by various emperors, the Northern Wei's Tuoba ancestors had practiced a half century or more of devotion to Buddhism, which was transmitted to China via Central and West Asia from India.

– Memorial

Notes: The Tuoba people had also mastered the art of casting statues and carving rocks into memorial images in honor of revered parents, relatives, and significant clan figures.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: A large number of structures and carvings at Longmen were destroyed caused by natural and man-made damage.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For economic reasons

– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– Periodically

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Buddha

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Buddha, Bodhisattvas, Ānanda, Arhat, and other Buddhist, Daoist, Christian, and other figures.

Notes: The grand entrance arch of the Huoshao Cave from the Northern Wei contains a relief of the Daoist immortals, the Queen Mother of the West and the King Father of the East, riding on dragons amid auspicious clouds.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– Yes

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– Yes

↳ Body present:

– Yes

Notes: Besides the temple caves, Longmen also has burial caves for high-ranking monks.

↳ Part of body present:

– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, the Tuoba clan.

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– Yes

↳ Part of body present:

– I don't know

Notes: The tomb of Bai Juyi (772–846), a most famous Tang poet, is at Longmen, and allegedly he was buried there. Scholarly representations of Longmen underwent three major changes during the Song-Yuan dynastic transition, while still acknowledging the heritage of the past. One was the reinvention of Bai Juyi as a “cultural ancestor” of Longmen and a role model for those seeking independence and detachment from officialdom.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

↳ Body present:

– No

Notes: Emperors such as Xiaowen were equated with the incarnation of the Tathāgata Buddha who represented the eternal essence of being, beyond all coming and going.

↳ Part of body present:
– Yes

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify
– King or emperor
– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity
– Private individual

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:
– Priests
– Slaves
– Corvee labourers
– Indentured servants
– Captured enemies
– Men
– Women
– Specialized labourers/craftspeople
– Other [specify]: official and private donors

Notes: Most images at Longmen came with inscribed epigraphs, an enormous number of donor inscriptions in stone, and other texts inscribed on the same stone side by side with the hewn rock images to which they refer. This level of epigraphic activity is largely absent at Yungang in Datong, Shanxi Province due to the culture and coarse-grained granite in the latter.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by semi-divine human(s)

Notes: The sage, king and sovereign, the legendary emperor, Yu the Great was closely associated with Luoyang's Longmen. To control flooding, Yu the Great is said to have organized large groups of laborers to dredge the riverbeds and open up the drainage channel that ran down the Longmen Hill. For over a millennium, the Longmen site was chiefly appreciated for its scenery, political and cultural heroes such as Yu the Great and Bai Juyi, and epigraphic inscriptions. Longmen's striking natural landscape (shanshui), rather than its stone niches and statues, was most often the center of attention. The turn of the twentieth century marked a watershed, when international studies of Longmen's caves and iconography began to appear in the fields of archaeology, sinology, religion, art, and East Asian studies.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The founding of the Western Zhou dynasty (1046 BCE-771 BCE)

Notes: Prominently featured in Chinese mythology and early records, Luoyang and Longmen were both sacred and imperial centers, in striking contrast to their post-thirteenth century decline. Located in a narrow, mountain-rimmed basin formed by the Rivers Yi and Luo, Luoyang was the capital of thirteen dynasties, the first of which was founded over 1,500 years before the Common Era. During the seventh century, Luoyang's status reached its zenith as a shendu (divine capital). According to historical data, the construction of Luoyi (Luoyang) began in the fifth year of the Duke of Zhou's regency when King Cheng of the Zhou was a boy.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: Luoyang's Longmen as a place has been used by both believers and nonbelievers for thousands of years.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: The Longmen Grottoes started its life initially as an expression of the royal, imperial, and ordinary people's devotion mainly to Buddhism.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Buddhist scriptures [Huayan, Chan, the Pure Land, Esotericism, the Dharmalakṣaṇa school (Yogācāra), etc.] at historical Longmen.

Notes: In 840, Bai sponsored the construction of the scripture hall at the Xiangshan Monastery; he is said to have donated 5,000 copies of the Buddhist scriptures and over 800 of his own poems, composed in Luoyang, to be kept there. During the Tang dynasty the Xiangshan Monastery was located at the south end of the East Hill and the southeast end of the nine Leigutai caves. The Xiangshan Monastery that exists and is in use today at Longmen was built in 1707 on the foundations of the Qianyuan Monastery, which dated from the Tang. See Wen Yucheng, "Luoyang Longmen Xiangshan Si yizhi diaochao shijue," *Kaogu*, no. 1 (1986): 40-3.

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Yes

↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

– Yes

↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:

This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

– Yes

↳ Space underneath the structure

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: It varies throughout history.

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– Yes

- ↳ Built specifically for the purpose:
 - Yes
- ↳ Repurposed:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they read aloud:
 - Yes
- ↳ To a human audience
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they studied:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they recopied:
 - Yes
- ↳ Used for divination:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: It depends on the specific periods of history.

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes

- ↳ On the outside:
 - Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Lotus, for instance.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There are stupas at Longmen as well.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Daoist gods are found at Longmen as well.

Notes: For example, the grand entrance arch of the Huoshao Cave from the Northern Wei contains a relief of the Daoist immortals, the Queen Mother of the West and the King Father of the East, riding on dragons amid auspicious clouds. During the Western Han dynasty (206 BCE–8 CE), the image of the Buddha was absorbed into existing Chinese religious and burial practices, similar to rites featuring native deities like the Queen Mother of the West.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The narratives of Greco-Buddhist communication and Chinese history are deeply intertwined in scholarly analysis of Longmen. The Central Binyang Cave at Longmen, which probably first caught the eye of the French travelers, is where the two most famous/infamous bas-reliefs “Emperor Xiaowen and His Court” and “Offering Procession of the Empress as Donor with Her Court” originally belonged. However, during the 1930s, the two bas-reliefs were removed and then sold to their current homes, the Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York City and the Nelson-Atkins Museum in Kansas City, respectively.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Stone low reliefs at Longmen

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– ‘True’ fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Unlike Dunhuang, wall color frescos are not a dominant feature at Longmen due to natural resources and environment.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: A diversity of religious and non-religious manifestations including mosaics can be seen at Longmen.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Epigraphic inscription mostly not standing along, but instead adjacent to the stone carvings at Longmen.

Notes: Aside from archaeology, our contemporary understanding and appreciation of Longmen's specimens is largely derived from epigraphy and iconography, two of the separate branches of historical, art, and aesthetic studies that converged in the early twentieth century.

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Drapes, hair knots, etc.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Apsara and dragon, for instance

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - Yes
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Clothing and hair styles

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 4.3

Notes: 4.3 square kilometers and 9.5 square kilometers. The boundaries of two special protected zones—"inner" and "general"—were demarcated. No buildings can be constructed within the "inner" protection zone—about 4.3 square kilometers, bounded by Yuziling to the east, Erdaoqiaogou to the south, the Yiluo highway to the west, and Meiyaogou to the north. In the

general protection zone—9.5 square kilometers, bounded by Shimagou in the east, Shuinichang in the south, Peijiayao in the west, and Yuanlinchang in the north—construction is restricted and must conform to relevant environmental regulations

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

—Height, meters: 17.14

Notes: Vairocana Buddha at Longmen. Among the Tang caves, the Fengxian Temple, also known as Jiujianfang, housing the 17.14-meter-high statue of the Huayan (Avataṃsaka) and esoteric Buddha Vairocana, is the most photographed, iconic monument of Longmen. Completed in 675/676 (and most probably started in 666), the Fengxian Temple was constructed by a team of workmen including Li Junzan, Cheng Renwei, and Yao Shiji, led by Wei Ji, Fan Xuanze, and two prominent master monks under the auspices of the Tang emperor Gaozong (r. 650–680).

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

— I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

—Height, meters: 4

Notes: The smallest niche at Longmen is 1.9 cm high, and the smallest sitting Buddha is 1.3 cm, both located in the Guyang Cave. The head of the largest image, Buddha Vairocana, is 4 meters long (with 1.9-meter-long ears), and its shoulders are 6 meters broad.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

— Yes

↳ Earth

— Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

— Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

— No

↳ Sand

— Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Dark limestone on site.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: pine trees, ivies, and other tree and plants at Longmen.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions

and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 4.3

Notes: 4.3 square kilometers and 9.5 square kilometers. The boundaries of two special protected zones—"inner" and "general"—were demarcated. No buildings can be constructed within the "inner" protection zone—about 4.3 square kilometers, bounded by Yuziling to the east, Erdaoqiaogou to the south, the Yiluo highway to the west, and Meiyaogou to the north. In the general protection zone—9.5 square kilometers, bounded by Shimagou in the east, Shuinichang in the south, Peijiayao in the west, and Yuanlinchang in the north—construction is restricted and must conform to relevant environmental regulations

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 17.14

Notes: Vairocana Buddha at Longmen. Among the Tang caves, the Fengxian Temple, also known as Jiujianfang, housing the 17.14-meter-high statue of the Huayan (Avataṃsaka) and esoteric Buddha Vairocana, is the most photographed, iconic monument of Longmen. Completed in 675/676 (and most probably started in 666), the Fengxian Temple was constructed by a team of workmen including Li Junzan, Cheng Renwei, and Yao Shiji, led by Wei Ji, Fan Xuanze, and two prominent master monks under the auspices of the Tang emperor Gaozong (r. 650–680).

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 4

Notes: The smallest niche at Longmen is 1.9 cm high, and the smallest sitting Buddha is 1.3 cm, both located in the Guyang Cave. The head of the largest image, Buddha Vairocana, is 4 meters long (with 1.9-meter-long ears), and its shoulders are 6 meters broad.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Dark limestone on site.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: pine trees, ivies, and other tree and plants at Longmen.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Lotus, for instance.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There are stupas at Longmen as well.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Daoist gods are found at Longmen as well.

Notes: For example, the grand entrance arch of the Huoshao Cave from the Northern Wei contains a relief of the Daoist immortals, the Queen Mother of the West and the King Father of the East, riding on dragons amid auspicious clouds. During the Western Han dynasty (206 BCE–8 CE), the image of the Buddha was absorbed into existing Chinese religious and burial practices, similar to rites featuring native deities like the

Queen Mother of the West.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The narratives of Greco-Buddhist communication and Chinese history are deeply intertwined in scholarly analysis of Longmen. The Central Binyang Cave at Longmen, which probably first caught the eye of the French travelers, is where the two most famous/infamous bas-reliefs “Emperor Xiaowen and His Court” and “Offering Procession of the Empress as Donor with Her Court” originally belonged. However, during the 1930s, the two bas-reliefs were removed and then sold to their current homes, the Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York City and the Nelson-Atkins Museum in Kansas City, respectively.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Stone low reliefs at Longmen

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Unlike Dunhuang, wall color frescos are not a dominant feature at Longmen due to natural resources and environment.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: A diversity of religious and non-religious manifestations including mosaics can be seen at Longmen.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: Epigraphic inscription mostly not standing along, but instead adjacent to the stone carvings at Longmen.

Notes: Aside from archaeology, our contemporary understanding and appreciation of Longmen's specimens is largely derived from epigraphy and iconography, two of the separate branches of historical, art, and aesthetic studies that converged in the early twentieth century.

↳ Other type of decoration:
– Yes [specify]: Drapes, hair knots, etc.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– Yes
Notes: Apsara and dragon, for instance

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– Yes

- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Clothing and hair styles

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

- optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

- Yes
- Notes: In the beginning of the rock carving around the 3th-5th century.

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

- Yes

↳ Birth

– I don't know

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Marriage

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– I don't know

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

– Yes

- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:
 - No
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:
 - No
- ↳ Is sex-deprivation required:
 - No
- ↳ Are intoxicants required:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Physical ordeal required:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Wild-animals
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Domesticated animals
 - Yes
 - ↳ Captive animals
 - I don't know
- ↳ Divination through non-living material:
 - Flame
 - Other [specify in comments]
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Water, tree, moon, crickets, rocks, etc.

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: It varies greatly in history and contemporary times. Today it can be thousands of participants.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Every year; several times every month

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– I don't know

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– I don't know

Notes: Longmen is not known for human sacrifices.

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Bad supernatural beings present as well.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Through accumulation of good deeds in life.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: This can be very individual in history and nowadays.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: This is very individual in history and now.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

–Yes [specify]: It varies. Some are held at the Fengxian Temple, some at held at the platform on the east side within Longmen, whereas some feasting are held at Xiangshan Monastery and other locations at Longmen.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Yearly, monthly, weekly

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: It varies. For festivals, it can be a few hundreds to ten thousands. Longmen has an average 3 million visitors per year.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Fruits, foods, charms, etc.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Through stone icons and images at Longmen.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– No

↳ Animal:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Buddhist stoen carvings

↳ Other

–Yes [specify]: Buddha and other Buddhist carvings

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

- ↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

- ↳ Is it required:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - No

- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Maintenance and repairs have been performed especially after Longmen was added to the UNESCO World Heritage List since 2001.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

- ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - Yes

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Family tomb/crypt:
 - Yes

- ↳ Domestic context:
 - Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Buddhist temples, caves

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Longmen is a place of both votive and secular.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Vairocana Buddha, e.g.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Buddhist, Daoist, Confucianist, Christian, and other forms of human-divine beings at present at Longmen. As André Malraux, one of Longmen's French admirers, put it, "Longmen is a world." André Malraux, *Le musée imaginaire de la sculpture mondiale: Des bas-reliefs aux grottes sacrées* (Paris, 1954), where Malraux implied that Longmen was an awe-inspiring repository of the past. Contemporary tour guides describe the site as a "huge museum," baoluo wanxiang (all encompassing), in agreement with Malraux.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– No

↳ Animal:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:
Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value
– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:
– Yes

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Buddhist stoen carvings

↳ Other
– Yes [specify]: Buddha and other Buddhist carvings

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– Yes

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:
– Yes

↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– Yes

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Buddhist temples, caves

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Bad supernatural beings present as well.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Through accumulation of good deeds in life.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Through stone icons and images at Longmen.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Longmen is a place of both votive and secular.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Vairocana Buddha, e.g.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Buddhist, Daoist, Confucianist, Christian, and other forms of human-divine beings at present at Longmen. As André Malraux, one of Longmen's French admirers, put it, "Longmen is a world." André Malraux, *Le musée imaginaire de la sculpture mondiale: Des bas-reliefs aux grottes sacrées* (Paris, 1954), where Malraux implied that Longmen was an awe-inspiring repository of the past. Contemporary tour guides describe the site as a "huge museum," *baoluo wanxiang* (all encompassing), in agreement with Malraux.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: This can be very individual in history and nowadays.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: This is very individual in history and now.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: It varies greatly in history and contemporary times. Today it can be thousands of participants.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Every year; several times every month

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– I don't know

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– I don't know

Notes: Longmen is not known for human sacrifices.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Fruits, foods, charms, etc.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Maintenance and repairs have been performed especially after Longmen was added to the UNESCO World Heritage List since 2001.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

Notes: In the beginning of the rock carving around the 3th-5th century.

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– I don't know

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Marriage

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

- ↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
 - Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - No

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: It varies. Some are held at the Fengxian Temple, some at held at the platform on the east side within Longmen, whereas some feasting are held at Xiangshan Monastery and other locations at Longmen.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: Yearly, monthly, weekly

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: It varies. For festivals, it can be a few hundreds to ten thousands. Longmen has an average 3 million visitors per year.

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– I don't know

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– No

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– I don't know

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– I don't know

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– Yes

↳ Wild-animals
– I don't know

↳ Domesticated animals
– Yes

↳ Captive animals
– I don't know

↳ Divination through non-living material:
– Flame
– Other [specify in comments]

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Water, tree, moon, crickets, rocks, etc.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:
– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:
– Yes

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: Bio parks, and marsh lands.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: Railway lines, the core of industrialization and modernization, have been built in Luoyang and at Longmen in the twentieth century. In an effort to apply successfully to the UNESCO World Heritage List in 1999/2000, the Jiaozhi railway line was moved 700 meters (0.43 miles) away from the site, and antivibration devices were mounted on the rail track. To protect the Longmen property from motor vehicles, the Luoluan and Luolin highways were relocated outside the protection area.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Longmen is part of the automobile roads, bus and subway lines.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– No

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Longmen is known also for its stupas and Nestorian burial niches that contained written texts.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Various agencies have been put in place to maintain Longmen in history and at present: e.g. In 1951, the Forest and Ancient Relics Committee of Longmen (Longmen Senlin Guji Baohu Weiyuanhui) was established; In April 1953, the Longmen wenwu baoguan suo (the Longmen Institute for the Protection of Relics 龙门文物保管所) was formed with only four staff members, and maintenance and repair work was conducted simultaneously. In September 1963, the Longmen Protection Area was demarcated. Weekly inspections were carried out by the Longmen Institute for the Protection of Relics until 1990. Throughout the 1970s–1980s, supported by the CCP Central Committee, measures were taken to strengthen the collapsing caves and preserve the sculptures. In 1982, Longmen was designated a site of national scenic importance. In 1990, the Longmen Institute briefly merged with the Longmen Institute for Landscape Management (Longmen Yuanlin Guanlisuo, Fengjingqu Guanbaochu) which shared the same office facilities under two separate names—Longmen Shiku Yanjiusuo (The Longmen Institute for Research) and Longmen Guanliju (the Longmen Scenery Management Bureau). However, in October 1992 the Longmen Institute for Research began operating as an independent unit once more, with seventy-two employees. In 2001, more than 1,500 years after the initial stone carving activities had ceased on the site, Longmen became a UNESCO World Heritage site under the protection of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention and Chinese law, prompting further urbanization and development in Luoyang. The following year, the Research Academy of the Longmen Grottoes (Longmen Yanjiuyuan, Longmen Research Academy for short) was founded to replace the Longmen Institute for Research, and has undergone large-scale expansion since that time. In 2007, Longmen became China's first national 5A-level scenic site, and the Longmen Research Academy fell under the newly formed Longmen Culture and Tourism Management Committee (Longmen Wenhua Lüyou Yuanqu Guanli Weiyuanhui), under whose auspices it continues to function. During the 2010s, the Longmen Research Academy began operating from a new office complex in the eastern corner of the main northeast entrance to the caves.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Various agencies have been put in place to maintain Longmen in history and at present: e.g. In 1951, the Forest and Ancient Relics Committee of Longmen (Longmen Senlin Guji Baohu Weiyuanhui) was established; In April 1953, the Longmen wenwu baoguansuo (the Longmen Institute for the Protection of Relics 龙门文物保管所) was formed with only four staff members, and maintenance and repair work was conducted simultaneously. In September 1963, the Longmen Protection Area was demarcated. Weekly inspections were carried out by the Longmen Institute for the Protection of Relics until 1990. Throughout the 1970s–1980s, supported by the CCP Central Committee, measures were taken to strengthen the collapsing caves and preserve the sculptures. In 1982, Longmen was designated a site of national scenic importance. In 1990, the Longmen Institute briefly merged with the Longmen Institute for Landscape Management (Longmen Yuanlin Guanlisuo, Fengjingqu Guanbaochu) which shared the same office facilities under two separate names—Longmen Shiku Yanjiusuo (The Longmen Institute for Research) and Longmen Guanlijū (the Longmen Scenery Management Bureau). However, in October 1992 the Longmen Institute for Research began operating as an independent unit once more, with seventy-two employees. In 2001, more than 1,500 years after the initial stone carving activities had ceased on the site, Longmen became a UNESCO World Heritage site under the protection of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention and Chinese law, prompting further urbanization and development in Luoyang. The following year, the Research Academy of the Longmen Grottoes (Longmen Yanjiuyuan, Longmen Research Academy for short) was founded to replace the Longmen Institute for Research, and has undergone large-scale expansion since that time. In 2007, Longmen became China's first national 5A-level scenic site, and the Longmen Research Academy fell under the newly formed Longmen Culture and Tourism Management Committee (Longmen Wenhua Lüyou Yuanqu Guanli Weiyuanhui), under whose auspices it continues to function. During the 2010s, the

Longmen Research Academy began operating from a new office complex in the eastern corner of the main northeast entrance to the caves.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Yes

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: Bio parks, and marsh lands.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: Railway lines, the core of industrialization and modernization, have been built in Luoyang and at Longmen in the twentieth century. In an effort to apply successfully to the UNESCO World Heritage List in 1999/2000, the Jiaozhi railway line was moved 700 meters (0.43 miles) away from the site, and antivibration devices were mounted on the rail track. To protect the Longmen property from motor vehicles, the Luoluan and Luolin highways were relocated outside the protection area.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Longmen is part of the automobile roads, bus and subway lines.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:
 - No
- ↳ Housed within the place/structure:
 - Yes
- ↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Longmen is known also for its stupas and Nestorian burial niches that contained written texts.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Madsen, Richard. The Sinicization of Chinese Religions: From Above and Below. BRILL, 2021. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Sinicization_of_Chinese_Religions_Fr.html?hl=&id=Kos5EAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Jenner, William. Memories of Loyang: Yang Hsuan-chih and the Lost Capital (439--534). Vol. 1. Clarendon Press, 1981.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Lu, Chaolin. Luoyang Longmen Zhi [洛阳龙门志 records on Luoyang's Longmen]. Vol. 2. Private, 1870.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Brown, Shana J.. Pastimes. University of Hawaii Press, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=VFkEEAAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Brook, Timothy, and Gregory Blue. China and Historical Capitalism. Cambridge University Press, 2002. https://books.google.com/books/about/China_and_Historical_Capitalism.html?hl=&id=rAFF94exLscC.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Zürcher, Erik. *The Buddhist Conquest of China*. BRILL, 2007.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Buddhist_Conquest_of_China.html?hl=&id=GYSKhU7UW-cC.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Wong, Aida Yuen. *The Other Kang Youwei*. Brill, 2015. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Other_Kang_Youwei.html?hl=&id=AfccswEACAAJ.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Li, Zonggui. *Between Tradition and Modernity*. Oxford: Chartridge Books, 2015.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Between_Tradition_and_Modernity.html?hl=&id=tJMMCAAQAQBAJ.

Reference: Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang, Henan Province of P. R. China, Chan, Pedith Pui. *The Making of a Modern Art World*. BRILL, 2017.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Making_of_a_Modern_Art_World.html?hl=&id=76y8DgAAQBAJ.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Elevation, Tree, grove, or forest, Water source, Body of water (as distinct from source), Marsh or bog, Cave, Other [specify]: grass, plants, flowers, Rothschild, N. Harry. *Emperor Wu Zhao and Her Pantheon of Devis, Divinities, and Dynastic Mothers*. Columbia University Press, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=mHmpBgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Elevation, Tree, grove, or forest, Water source, Body of water (as distinct from source), Marsh or bog, Cave, Other [specify]: grass, plants, flowers, Wang, Dong. *Longmen's Stone Buddhas and Cultural Heritage*. Rowman & Littlefield, 2020.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Longmen_s_Stone_Buddhas_and_Cultural_Her.html?hl=&id=s5XnDwAAQBAJ. fig.0.1

Reference: Elevation, Tree, grove, or forest, Water source, Body of water (as distinct from source), Marsh or bog, Cave, Other [specify]: grass, plants, flowers, Hughes, April D.. *Worldly Saviors and Imperial Authority in Medieval Chinese Buddhism*. University of Hawaii Press, 2021.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Worldly_Saviors_and_Imperial_Authority_i.html?hl=&id=LDcWEAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Elevation, Tree, grove, or forest, Water source, Body of water (as distinct from source), Marsh or bog, Cave, Other [specify]: grass, plants, flowers, McNair, Amy. *Donors of Longmen*. University of Hawaii Press, 2007. https://books.google.com/books/about/Donors_of_Longmen.html?hl=&id=qsEGldhcgMoC.